

1 **Investigational transcriptomics of palezestrant and elecestrant, estrogen receptor degraders**
2 **utilized for treatment of ESR1 mutant breast cancer.**

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8 We studied total transcription in cells treated with palezestrant and elecestrant, estrogen receptor
9 degraders used in patients with acquired ESR1 mutation during treatment resistance. Elacestrant induced
10 alterations in cell cycle featuring reductions in *MKI67* and *MYBL2* and in cyclins like *CCNA2* but with
11 mixed effect on *CDKN* induction. The spindle and kinetochore were noticeably affected by elacestrant,
12 with decreased quantities of *TPX2* and centrosome proteins like *CENPN*. Elacestrant silenced *GREB1*
13 expression and expression of the progesterone receptor (*PGR*), demonstrating estrogen receptor
14 degrader control of hormone signaling.
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